

ADVANCED MATERIALS AND THE EU GREEN DEAL: SUNRISE CASE STUDY INSIGHTS ON REGULATION, CHALLENGES, AND OPPORTUNITIES

CONSOLIDATED SUMMARY REPORT BASED ON THREE CASE STUDY INTERVIEWS CONDUCTED IN SUNRISE TASK 6.2

Ghaya Rziga, Oona Freudenthal, Blanca Suarez-Merino, Lasse Steffens

Sunrise has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under the Grant Agreement No. 101137324. Swiss partners have received national funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education Research and Innovation (SERI).

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This report constitutes the Part I of the “Deliverable 6.2: SUNRISE contribution to the policy landscape”.

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Publication Date: April 2026

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
AdMa	Advanced Materials
BPR	Biocidal Products Regulation (Regulation (EU) No 528/2012)
CAS	Chemical Abstracts Service
CE	Conformité Européenne
CLP	Classification, Labelling and Packaging Regulation (Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008)
CEN	European Committee for Standardization (Comité Européen de Normalisation)
DSD	Dangerous Substances Directive
ECHA	European Chemicals Agency
EC	European Commission
EoL	End-of-Life
EU	European Union
GMP	Good Manufacturing Practices
GRAS	Generally Recognised as Safe
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MSDS	Material Safety Data Sheet
NMs	Nanomaterials
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
PPE	Personal Protective Equipment
PPP	Plant Protection Products
R&D	Research and Development
REACH	Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006)
SDS	Safety Data Sheet
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SSbD	Safe and Sustainable by Design

SUNRISE	Project acronym (full name not required)
TDS	Technical Data Sheet
TiO₂	Titanium Dioxide
UV	Ultraviolet
WNT	Working Group of National Coordinators of the OECD Test Guidelines Programme
WPMN	OECD Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials

1. INTRODUCTION

This report presents a consolidated summary of the interviews conducted under Task 6.2 of the SUNRISE project. The objective of this task is to establish a policy communication channel between SUNRISE and relevant policy stakeholders, ensuring that the project's research activities and outcomes align with ongoing regulatory developments and emerging policy priorities at both the European and international levels.

Task 6.2 builds on the policy strategy map developed in Task 6.1 and aims to strengthen the project's contribution to policy dialogue by connecting SUNRISE to key regulatory fora and initiatives. As part of this effort, a series of interviews were carried out with three industrial case studies representing different application areas of advanced materials: cosmetics (CompLife), anticorrosive coatings (Lurederra), and biocides for post-harvest preservation (Laurentia). The interviews aimed to collect insights from the case study partners regarding their awareness of current regulations, the challenges and opportunities they face in the evolving policy landscape, and their views on the future direction of sustainable and safe advanced materials under the European Green Deal¹. These interviews complement the policy mapping conducted in Task 6.1.

The interviews were conducted using a structured questionnaire, which covered several key themes, including regulatory awareness, gaps and challenges in existing standards, innovation opportunities, policy impacts, support needs, and future regulatory outlook. The findings from these discussions have been consolidated and analysed to identify common trends, differences, and actionable insights.

¹ European Commission. *The European Green Deal*. COM (2019) 640 final. 11 December 2019. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF

2. METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of the interviews, LIST prepared a questionnaire template (see Annex 1), which was shared with the SUNRISE WP6 T6.2 partners for their review and the subsequent use. The questions focused on specific key themes, including regulatory awareness of the industrial partners, the challenges and gaps they identify in existing regulations and standards, the opportunities for innovation, the impact of policies on the processes and advanced materials (AdMa) produced, the types of support still needed, and the outlook regarding future regulatory developments and their influence on procedures and products.

Once consolidated, the above-mentioned questionnaire was distributed to the case study partners, who first received the written questions and provided written replies. This was followed by individual interviews to discuss further and clarify the responses. The interviews were conducted by the partners responsible for each case study: LIST interviewed the cosmetics case study (CompLife), TEMASOL carried out the interview with anticorrosive coatings case study (Lurederra), and BOKU conducted the interview with the biocide case study (Laurentia). While the same questionnaire was used across all three interviews, differences in interviewers and interviewing styles may have influenced the responses and the type of information extracted.

Within the SUNRISE project Task 6.2 also a stakeholder mapping was conducted to identify potential stakeholder targets and channels for the dissemination of the findings. In the following section 3 “Results of the policy mapping and identified stakeholders”, the list of stakeholders and the preferred dissemination channels identified by the project partners are presented.

In section 3 “Insight from the case studies”, we provide a consolidated summary and analysis of the responses from the three case studies, organised according to the guiding questions and main discussion topics.

Note that a second round of interviews is planned before the end of the project to capture updates and further reflections from the case studies.

3. RESULTS OF THE POLICY MAPPING AND IDENTIFIED STAKEHOLDERS

As part of the SUNRISE Task 6.1, a detailed mapping of relevant policies across the different life cycle stages of the three case study products was carried out, using the European Green Deal as the overarching framework. The full analysis will be available within the Task 6.1 deliverables; however, to provide a small overview, Table 1 below highlights the key policies identified concerning the case studies of this project.

When comparing the three case study sectors, several common policies and regulations clearly stand out as essential to the governance of advanced materials. These include:

- REACH (EC 1907/2006), which is crucial for all materials (hybrid UV filters, bio-sourced biocides, nanocoatings) especially for the registration procedures, safety data sheets, and hazard/risk assessment;
- CLP (EC 1272/2008) regarding the classification and labelling obligations for all substances and mixtures;
- the Industrial Emissions Directive (2010/75/EU) which is relevant for the production sites, emissions, and industrial processes in all three case studies; and
- the Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC) and its revision, defining waste management obligations and end-of-life requirements.

Additionally, further policies that are more case study specific like Cosmetics Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 unique to the cosmetics case study and Biocidal Products Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 mainly relevant for the biocide case study, were identified.

In addition to the above-mentioned regulatory pillars, several emerging Green Deal–driven frameworks are expected to shape the future development and assessment of advanced materials. These include:

- the Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR);
- the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) Framework;
- the Critical Raw Materials Act, which could influence the sourcing of raw materials; and
- the proposed Green Claims initiative, which could impose stricter rules on environmental marketing and sustainability communication.

The project partners also identified few relevant stakeholders for dissemination of the findings. These are mainly EU agencies such as the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) and European Food Safety Authority (EFSA), organisations involved in methodology development and standardisation like Joint Research Centre (JRC), European Committee for Standardization (CEN), Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and specifically the OECD Working Party on Manufactured Nanomaterials (WPMN) and Working Group of National Coordinators for the Test Guidelines Programme (WNT).

Table 1: Overview of key policies, regulations & standards across the three case studies based on the findings from T6.1

Policy / Regulation / Standard	Ambrosia (Cosmetics)	Laurentia (Biocides)	Lurederra (Anticorrosive coatings)
REACH – Regulation (EC) 1907/2006	yes	yes	yes
CLP – Regulation (EC) 1272/2008	yes	yes	yes
Industrial Emissions Directive (IED) – Directive 2010/75/EU	yes	yes	yes
Packaging & Packaging Waste Directive – Directive 94/62/EC	yes	yes	yes
Waste Framework Directive – Directive 2008/98/EC	yes	yes	yes
Directive 2004/37/EC (Carcinogens & Mutagens at Work)	yes	yes	yes
Critical Raw Materials Act (2023)	yes	yes	yes
ISO 14040:2006 – Life Cycle Assessment	yes	yes	yes
Eco-design for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR)	yes	yes (indirectly)	yes
Green Claims Initiative	yes	(some relevance)	(minor relevance)
Cosmetics Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009	yes	-	-
Nagoya Protocol (Access & Benefit Sharing)	yes	-	-
EU Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy	yes	-	yes
Single-Use Plastics Directive - Directive (EU) 2019/904	yes	-	yes
Biocidal Products Regulation - Regulation (EU) 528/2012	-	yes	-
Marine Strategy Framework Directive - 2008/56/EC	-	yes (indirectly)	yes

Directive 2013/39/EU (Water pollutants – WFD amendment)	-	yes	yes
Marine Spatial Planning Directive – 2014/89/EU	-	-	yes
ISO 19030-1:2016 (Hull & Propeller Performance)	-	-	yes
ISO 12944 Series (Corrosion Protection of Steel Structures)	-	-	yes
RoHS – Directive 2011/65/EU (Restriction of Hazardous Substances)	-	-	yes
Occupational Exposure Rules for Essential Oils	-	yes	-

4. INSIGHT FROM THE CASE STUDIES

4.1. GENERAL CONTEXT

4.1.1 CASE STUDY OVERVIEW AND USE OF ADVANCED MATERIALS

A brief description of the three case studies and their developed Advanced Materials (AdMa) is provided in this section. The case studies are representing different industrial sectors and applications and are illustrating the diverse ways in which AdMa are being designed and integrated into final products. Each example highlights the technological innovation and sustainability objectives of their development and use. Further information on the case studies can be found on the SUNRISE project website².

A. Case study on cosmetics - TiO₂-Based photoprotective Advanced Material

The cosmetics case study focuses on the development of AdMa in the field of photoprotection. The aim is to design and formulate next-generation sunscreen agents that enhance UV-filtering performance, with the ultimate goal of minimizing skin-related risks associated with sun exposure. The AdMa is based on a physical UV filter, TiO₂, which has well documented photoprotective properties as well as potential ecotoxicological effects. The TiO₂ particles are coated with a lipopeptide, which is designed to enhance UV-blocking performance while simultaneously improving the environmental impact compared to other coated forms of TiO₂ available on the market.

B. Case study on Anticorrosive coatings - Advanced anticorrosive coating for metallic surfaces

The Anticorrosive coatings case study focuses on anticorrosive coatings for harsh conditions focusing on metallic surfaces, mainly for many different classes of carbon steel but also suitable for aluminium. The AdMa is a combination of compounds which generate a final liquid formulation and provides a combination of functionalities; matrix compound, zinc flakes, and nanoalumina as ceramic nanomaterial, which provides hardness and chemical resistance, and finally a solvent (ethanol), to allow mixing of all components. The coating is a low thickness layer (less than 50 µm) and different in composition to a conventional paint, which are generally organic. End of life experiments have been performed following accelerated aging methodologies and have classified the material as C5H (high corrosivity, high humidity) following ISO 12944³.

C. Case study on a biocide - Microencapsulated natural oils for fruit preservation

The biocide case study develops microencapsulated natural oils for post-harvest fruit preservation. The capsules contain antifungal oils (glove oil, lavender) and are used in a water-based wax coating applied to fruit to prevent fungal spoilage during transport. These post-harvest fruit coatings allow to extend the shelf life of the fruits at the point of sale.

² SUNRISE project website: <https://www.sunrise-horizon.eu/sunrise-case-studies>

³ ISO 12944 – Paints and varnishes – Corrosion protection of steel structures by protective paint systems. [ISO 12944-1:2017 - Paints and varnishes – Corrosion protection of steel structures by protective paint systems – Part 1: General introduction](#)

4.1.2 SUSTAINABILITY GOALS AND ENVIRONMENTAL OBJECTIVES

The three case studies have introduced innovation to enhance sustainability and aimed their research to increase the resources efficiency as well as the use of safer products. Table 2 summarises these aspects.

Table 2: Summary of the key innovative aspects and sustainability approaches of the three SUNRISE case studies.

Case study	AdMa/Innovation	Sustainability approach	Environmental safety	End-of-life
Cosmetics	TiO ₂ selected due to its superior UV protection. The aim is to mitigate the side-effects of inorganic filters through improved coating technologies.	The coating is derived via microbial fermentation, reducing reliance on synthetic or hazardous surfactants by using agro-industrial by-products and supporting a circular production model.	Preliminary ecotoxicity tests on freshwater algae and zebrafish showed no significant toxicity, though further long-term studies are ongoing under the SUNRISE project.	Degradation behaviour in aquatic environments remains uncertain. Ongoing research is simulating marine and freshwater conditions to assess stability and dissociation. Early results indicate the hybrid material remains structurally stable.
Anti-corrosive coatings	A liquid formulation combining a matrix compound, zinc flakes for corrosion resistance, nanoalumina for hardness and chemical resistance, and ethanol as a solvent.	Unlike conventional organic paints, this coating is inorganic, forming a low-thickness layer (<50 µm) with enhanced protective properties. Temperature in the process is reduced as well as the amount of water	Low thickness coating (one-layer protection) for less weight on structures, less issues with mechanical tolerance, less toxic chemicals and less energetic resources involved (low-temperature curing and no need for mixing/dilution).	End-of-life testing using accelerated aging methods confirmed the coating's durability, classifying it as C5H (high corrosivity, high humidity) according to ISO 12944 standards.
Biocides	Microencapsulated natural oils (glove oil, lavender)	Longer self-life of antifungal products. Better safety/cost	The objective is to replace chitosan and formaldehyde based nanocapsules in post-	N/A

		balance of antifungal products. Fruit waste reduction.	harvest coatings to avoid the migration of these substances to into the fruit. The case study reuses treatment solutions and minimizes water use.	
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4.1.3 PERCEPTION AND IMPACT OF THE EUROPEAN GREEN DEAL: AWARENESS, PERCEPTION, AND SPECIFIC IMPACTS OF THE GREEN DEAL ON THE CASE STUDY

All the case study partners were aware of the Green Deal and the relative EU policies, which could be anticipated as they all are participating in a Horizon project addressing the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework. The cosmetics case study partner perceives it as a guiding framework for advancing materials science and sustainable (cosmetic) ingredient development. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner views their approach as more aligned with Green Deal goals than current market benchmarks. On the other hand, the biocide case study partner recognizes the importance of the Green Deal but highlighted a mismatch between Green Deal ambitions and current regulatory frameworks which often lag behind the Green Deal goals, particularly concerning the registration of natural substances according to the Phytosanitary Regulation⁴ (EU 2024/3115).

Clearly, based on the case studies of the SUNRISE project, the EU Green Deal has influenced product development by steering innovation toward safer, more sustainable, and circular solutions. The cosmetics case study integrates biotechnology and green chemistry to minimize environmental toxicity, aligning with the SSbD principles. The Anticorrosive coatings case study adapts its product design with the purpose to reduce harmful substances, such as fluor-based compounds, and prioritizes low-toxicity, energy-efficient coatings, although the environmental release assessments for these products remain limited due to technical constraints⁵. The biocide case study shares the Green Deal’s sustainability goals through the use of natural, non-toxic substances but faces regulatory barriers in registering these materials. Further regulatory awareness as well as gaps are discussed in the chapters below.

4.2. REGULATORY AND INDUSTRY STANDARD AWARENESS AND ENGAGEMENT

This section summarises the case studies’ level of awareness and engagement with the regulatory frameworks relevant to the specific AdMa used. The interviews explored three main aspects: (a) the

⁴ Phytosanitary Regulation (EU 2024/3115) <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/3115/oj/eng>

⁵ Technical constraints related to: 1) the high variability of scenarios of the use phase; 2) Experiments through climatic chambers not prepared to analyse the water collected during sampling.

regulatory landscape currently influencing their work and the life cycle stages most affected; (b) the use of voluntary standards and certifications to support compliance or market positioning; and (c) the level of information and preparedness regarding upcoming regulatory changes or new policy developments.

All three case studies are influenced by key EU regulations such as REACH⁶ and the CLP⁷ Regulation, though their levels of regulatory engagement vary based on their roles and product types. The cosmetics case study partner is directly involved in product development and commercialization of cosmetic ingredients and thus is fully engaged with a broad regulatory framework, including REACH, CLP, and the Cosmetics⁸ Regulation. These affect the full life cycle of the product—from production to safety testing, use, and end-of-life.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner, as a technology centre, is less directly involved in regulatory compliance. They develop formulations at a pilot scale but do not commercialize products themselves. Regulations and standards such as REACH, CLP, and CE marking are acknowledged, but regulatory responsibilities are handled by a spin-off company. Due to limited resources typical of SMEs, regulatory roles are often combined with other functions.

The biocide case study develops plant-based antifungal treatments and operates under REACH, CLP, and phytosanitary regulations, with their product registered as a plant protection product⁹ (PPP) rather than a biocide¹⁰. Their regulatory focus is mainly on the manufacturing and application stages of the product lifecycle.

Engagement with voluntary standards also varies among the case study partners. The cosmetics case study actively applies ISO standards - notably ISO 24444:2019¹¹ - to validate product performance (e.g., UV filtering efficacy), enhancing both compliance and marketability. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner is ISO 9001¹² certified, reflecting a commitment to quality management, but does not pursue ecolabels. The biocide case study partner is currently evaluating the use of ecolabels for future marketing purposes but hasn't yet adopted any formal certifications.

To conclude, the three case studies show strong awareness and proactive approaches to the existing and upcoming EU policy and legislative developments, which is a feature that aligns with the participation in the SUNRISE project. For example, the cosmetics case study partner stays updated through webinars, conferences, and EU publications. The Anticorrosive coatings case study remains well-informed and at the

⁶ **REACH Regulation** European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EC) No 1907/2006 concerning the Registration, Evaluation, Authorisation and Restriction of Chemicals (REACH)*. [EUR-Lex - 02006R1907-20250901 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

⁷ **CLP Regulation** European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EC) No 1272/2008 on classification, labelling and packaging of substances and mixtures (CLP)*. [EUR-Lex - 02008R1272-20250901 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

⁸ **Cosmetics Regulation** European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EC) No 1223/2009 on cosmetic products*. [EUR-Lex - 02009R1223-20250901 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

⁹ **Plant Protection Products Regulation (PPPR)** European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EC) No 1107/2009 concerning the placing of plant protection products on the market*. [EUR-Lex - 02009R1107-20221121 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

¹⁰ **Biocidal Products Regulation (BPR)** European Parliament and Council. *Regulation (EU) No 528/2012 concerning the making available on the market and use of biocidal products*. [EUR-Lex - 02012R0528-20240611 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

¹¹ **ISO 24444:2019** – Cosmetics – Sun protection test methods – In vivo determination of the sun protection factor (SPF). [ISO 24444:2019 - Cosmetics – Sun protection test methods – In vivo determination of the sun protection factor \(SPF\)](#)

¹² **ISO 9001:2015** – Quality management systems – Requirements. [ISO 9001:2015 - Quality management systems – Requirements](#)

forefront of AdMa innovation through its involvement in EU-funded projects. At the same time, the biocide case study relies on industry associations for regular regulatory updates. Table 3 summarizes the applicable regulations, followed standards as well as the approaches of the case study holders to keep up to date with policy evolution.

Table 3: Applicable regulations, level of engagement, followed standards as well as means to keep up to date with policy evolutions per case study partner.

Case study partner	Applicable regulations	Level of regulatory engagement	Followed standards	Means of keeping up to date with policy evolution
Cosmetics	REACH, CLP, Cosmetics regulation	Direct	ISO 24444:2019	Webinars, conferences, EU publications
Anticorrosive coatings	REACH, CLP, CE marking	Indirect	ISO 9001	EU-funded projects,
Biocide	REACH, CLP, phytosanitary	Direct	N/A	Industry associations

4.3. CHALLENGES AND GAPS

This section presents the main challenges and regulatory gaps identified through the case study interviews. In fact, the discussion focused on several key areas: (a) compliance challenges faced when meeting current or emerging regulatory requirements for advanced materials; (b) issues related to material safety assessments, data availability, and transparency; (c) legislative gaps, overlaps, and areas in need of improvement; (d) experiences with integrating eco-design principles within the existing regulatory context; and (e) obstacles related to circularity requirements, including recyclability and biodegradability. The following subsections summarise the main insights shared by the case studies across these themes.

A. Compliance challenges with current or emerging regulations: Difficulties in meeting regulatory requirements for advanced materials

The case studies are providing innovating material and product research aligning with EU sustainability goals; however, they face different types of compliance hurdles from regulatory ambiguity (cosmetics case study) to standard rigidity (Anticorrosive coatings case study) and registration burdens (biocide case study).

The cosmetics case study faces complex regulatory hurdles at the intersection of nanomaterials, cosmetics, and environmental safety. Their advanced material, as a hybrid of TiO₂ and a biosurfactant (surfactin), falls into regulatory grey zones:

- REACH and Cosmetic Regulation require separate safety data for nanomaterials, but the standardized methods for characterizing hybrid materials are lacking.
- Current regulations don't clearly define or classify surface-functionalized or hybrid nanomaterials, which makes the compliance ambiguous and inconsistent.
- Companies sometimes bypass scrutiny by listing components separately (e.g., TiO₂ and surfactin individually), while the cosmetics case study partner of SUNRISE aims for more transparent classification.
- Emerging frameworks, like the SSbD, demand life cycle-based assessments, but practical tools and methodologies for such assessments are still underdeveloped.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study encounters compliance issues not with chemical regulations, but with standards misaligned with innovation in coatings.

- Their thin-layer nanocoatings (< 50 µm) offer excellent performance but don't meet the ISO 12944-9:2018¹³ standard, which requires much thicker coatings (280–800 µm).
- Similarly, ASTM D4060 abrasion tests are not suitable for very thin coatings, potentially disqualifying them despite strong real-world performance.

These outdated or ill-fitting standards pose a barrier to market entry. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner has taken steps to influence change by participating in standardisation work, notably under ISO/TC 35/SC 14¹⁴.

The biocide case study struggles primarily with phytosanitary regulatory frameworks, which are costly and time-consuming when registering new natural substances. These regulative limitations hinder the adoption of more sustainable, natural antifungal treatments in post-harvest applications. Despite aiming to replace synthetic, hazardous substances (e.g., formaldehyde), the regulatory environment makes market access difficult for innovative plant-based alternatives.

The common challenges that the interviews highlighted are the fact that compliance, especially for new materials or natural substances, demands significant resources, disproportionately affecting SMEs and research-driven developers. Additionally, all three case studies face challenges where existing frameworks don't fit emerging technologies or material formats (hybrids, nanocoatings, natural substances).

B. Material safety and data transparency issues: Challenges in safety assessments, data availability, and transparency

The three case studies identify a gap in safety data for the AdMa or the non-standard materials (e.g. natural substances). Hence there is a need for more adapted safety protocols that reflect new formulations and

¹³ ISO 12944-9:2018 Paints and varnishes — Corrosion protection of steel structures by protective paint systems Part 9: Protective paint systems and laboratory performance test methods for offshore and related structures

¹⁴ ISO TC 35/SC 14 Protective paint systems for steel structures. [ISO/TC 35/SC 14 - Protective paint systems for steel structures](#)

processes (e.g., hybrids, nanomaterials, natural substances). There is also a need to improve the data transparency through dedicated testing or improved Safety Data Sheets (SDS).

The cosmetics case study partner faces significant challenges in safety assessment due to the hybrid nature of its material (TiO₂ and biosurfactant). While each component individually (TiO₂, surfactant) is generally regarded as safe, the data on the hybrid's long-term toxicity is lacking. The standardized protocols for safety testing of hybrid organic-inorganic materials are currently absent, which complicates the evaluation of hazards. The partner relies on proxy data but emphasizes the need to treat and test hybrid materials as new entities, not just component-based assessments. They suggest the SSbD framework could benefit from more flexibility at the pilot scale, such as relaxing Good Manufacturing Practices (GMP) requirements to facilitate earlier testing and development.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study identified a lack of comprehensive technical and safety data in existing documentation. SDS and Technical Data Sheets (TDS) often do not adequately cover the advanced ingredients, especially nanoparticles and additives. In response, and in order to improve transparency and internal tracking, the case study partners are developing an internal database to generate more complete and better tailored SDS for their innovative formulations.

The biocide case study partner's safety concerns are related to the replacement of toxic cross-linkers in biopolymer formulations. Their challenge is how to maintain product performance while switching to safer alternatives. Although they did not report major gaps in data availability, ensuring safety without compromising sustainability goals remains an ongoing challenge.

C. Legislative gaps, overlaps, and improvement needs: Identifying shortcomings in the current regulatory framework

The three case studies call for regulatory updates to keep track with the innovation in AdMa. This includes updating classification systems, enabling cross-sector alignment, incorporating natural and hybrid materials into regulatory frameworks, and fostering safe innovation through better data transparency and guidance.

The cosmetics case study partner highlights significant gaps in the classification and regulation of hybrid nanomaterials, noting the lack of standardized testing methods and conflicting requirements across sectors (e.g., cosmetics, REACH, nanomaterials). These inconsistencies hinder the timely market entry of safer and sustainable products. The case stresses the need for clearer guidance, harmonized definitions, and adapted safety testing frameworks that reflect the nature of emerging materials.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study emphasizes the importance of improving access to and quality of material data. They propose the creation of a database containing analytical characterizations of advanced materials (e.g. from different EU projects and R&D).

The biocide case study points out a misalignment between sustainability ambitions (e.g., the EU Green Deal) and current chemical and phytosanitary regulations. Many natural, safer alternatives are excluded from approved substance lists, which limits innovation and market adoption of greener solutions. They call for regulatory updates that better reflect and enable the transition to bio-based, low-toxicity materials.

D. Eco-design Integration in Regulatory Context: Experience with integrating eco-design principles under existing rules

The three case studies demonstrate a shared commitment to eco-design, though their experiences vary depending on sector, material type, and regulatory complexity.

The cosmetics case study partner sees eco-design as both a regulatory opportunity and a market driver, especially in the context of developing hybrid UV-filtering AdMa like TiO₂ and sodium surfactin. They view increasing regulatory support for sustainability, the potential for standardization as well as increasing market demand for green alternatives, as enablers. However, implementation is still hindered by the regulatory issues previously mentioned.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner has made tangible progress in applying eco-design to product development. Their strategies include modifying nanoparticle behaviour (e.g., dispersion in liquid, encapsulation, core-shell structures) to minimize environmental and human health risks, prevent release, and improve compatibility with ecosystems. These technical adjustments are aligned with eco-design goals and are carried out despite some misalignment with conventional standards.

The biocide case study partner finds eco-design more challenging, primarily due to regulatory hurdles in material approval and the complexity of assessing full life-cycle impacts. For instance, while using natural oils seems sustainable, their extraction processes can be energy-intensive, potentially offsetting environmental benefits. The regulatory system does not yet fully support or reward such nuanced eco-design trade-offs.

E. Circularity Requirements and Related Challenges: Specific obstacles related to recyclability and biodegradability

The cosmetics case study partner's work with hybrid UV-filtering materials (TiO₂ and biosurfactant) highlights the complexity of achieving recyclability and biodegradability in composite systems. They mention several challenges:

- Lack of standardized end-of-life (EoL) assessments for hybrid materials.
- Conflicting degradation behaviours: TiO₂ is persistent in the environment, while the surfactants may degrade.
- Unclear environmental fate: No regulatory guidance exists for assessing hybrid dissociation or its impact.
- Regulatory fragmentation: REACH and Cosmetics Regulation assess components separately, ignoring synergistic effects.

Hence, they propose that there should be hybrid-specific EoL tests and harmonized definitions to better track degradation and minimize environmental footprint.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study faces challenges related to recyclability and biodegradability, especially when trying to maintain the same material performance. Efforts to recycle Polyvinyl Butyral (PVB)

from car windscreens showed that technical feasibility is not enough, but market acceptance and regulatory clarity are equally vital. Furthermore, recycled materials face resistance from industry, often due to aesthetic or compositional categorization. On biodegradability, current materials with high performance rarely match their non-biodegradable counterparts, indicating the need for further R&D.

The biocide case study partner emphasizes that bio-based materials, while promising for sustainability, have their own circularity trade-offs. As previously mentioned, the extraction of natural oils and biopolymers is resource- and energy-intensive, which can offset environmental benefits. Furthermore, client reluctance is a significant barrier and without regulatory pressure or bans on petrochemical inputs, many customers are not incentivized to adopt greener alternatives.

It is thus clear that challenges remain concerning circularity requirements within the applied domains of AdMa. The challenges primarily highlighted within the case studies of the SUNRISE project include regulatory issues and environmental concerns, while stakeholder and market acceptance were also emphasized.

4.4. OPPORTUNITIES AND AREAS OF EASE

In addition to identifying challenges and regulatory issues, the interviews explored how existing European policies and regulations have positively influenced the development of advanced materials within the SUNRISE case studies. In this section, we present how the interview discussions explored three key aspects: (a) regulations or policy measures that have supported or streamlined research and innovation processes; (b) regulatory drivers that have created opportunities for technological advancement, competitive advantage, or new market access; and (c) policy elements or regulatory procedures that were considered clear, effective, or exemplary in facilitating compliance and sustainable innovation. This section summarises the insights gathered from the three case studies under the above-mentioned themes.

For the cosmetics case study the European Green Deal has been a strategic enabler, encouraging sustainable innovation in their hybrid UV-filter materials. REACH and CLP Regulations also provide a robust framework that supports safe material development across the life cycle. The cosmetics case study partner relies on the local and policy-driven synergies, in fact their proximity to Italy's Food Valley enabled access to agro-industrial by-products (e.g., tomato, wine waste), which supports circular practices. Hence, they succeeded in transforming grape pomace into high-value Hyaluronic acid, illustrating how upcycling and regulation can create economically and environmentally beneficial outcomes. However, financial incentives are still needed to offset the high R&D and regulatory compliance costs.

The cosmetics case study partners see that the regulatory emphasis on safety and sustainability has incentivized innovation in hybrid UV filters. Their hybrid design aims to reduce environmental persistence by leveraging the biodegradable nature of the surfactant to mitigate TiO₂'s environmental impact. The drive for eco-innovation should enhance the product marketability, especially with growing consumer demand for green cosmetics.

From the cosmetics case study partners' perspective, the Green Deal's focus on sustainable innovation is particularly clear and enabling. It encourages eco-friendly technologies like their biotech-based surfactants from agro-waste.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partners have confirmed that policies aligned with the Green Deal have directly influenced their product concepts and positioning. The regulatory momentum around sustainability has enhanced the relevance of their innovations. While their materials may be more expensive, policy-driven emphasis on sustainability has helped frame their performance-per-weight or area (L/m²) as a competitive advantage in the market. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner actively aims to stay ahead of regulatory trends but has not identified any part of the regulatory or policy process that they would consider particularly clear or easy to work with.

For the biocide case study, the EU bans on harmful phytosanitary substances and support for eco-labelled products have created space for sustainable alternatives to enter the market. These policy moves have incentivized innovation in biopolymer- and plant-based solutions, aligning regulatory restrictions with emerging market demand. The Green Deal policies are seen as a competitive enabler, provided that alternatives meet the necessary cost and performance thresholds.

To conclude, while challenges persist, existing EU regulations and sustainability policies have positively influenced R&D, market access, and eco-design, according to the case studies of the SUNRISE project. The alignment between policy objectives and technological innovation is gradually creating a supportive ecosystem for advancing AdMa in a safe and sustainable direction.

4.5. IMPLEMENTATION AND SUPPORT NEEDS

This section examines the practical aspects of policy implementation as experienced by the SUNRISE case studies. Through the interviews, we explored four main areas: (a) the types of support tools and mechanisms needed to facilitate policy compliance, including clearer guidelines, technical assistance, and financial incentives; (b) the quality of collaboration between industry and policymakers and potential areas for improvement; (c) the availability and usefulness of tools, training, and networks that support companies in managing compliance and regulatory knowledge; and (d) the lifecycle stages where environmental policy implementation presents the greatest challenges. The following parts present the findings from the interviews on these areas.

A. Support needs for policy compliance: Desired support tools, guidelines, technical help and financial incentives

While current regulations and sustainability policies have opened valuable opportunities for innovation and market positioning, the case studies also highlight that achieving and maintaining compliance requires significant support. The following outlines the key tools, guidance, and incentives needed to bridge policy ambitions with practical implementation.

Across the cosmetics, Anticorrosive coatings, and biocide case studies, there is a strong call for clearer, more integrated guidance tailored to the realities of advanced materials, alongside technical support tools and financial mechanisms to offset the high cost of compliance.

The cosmetics case study partner mentions that it needs clear, harmonized guidelines adaptable to a wide variety of hybrid materials, reducing uncertainty in compliance. It emphasizes financial incentives to help offset higher consumer prices and R&D costs, especially for SMEs. However, given that the EU Green Claims¹⁵ framework remains non-binding, it enables the widespread of false sustainability claims that undermine credible innovators which is in their view a policy-practice gap. Hence, they request for targeted funding for sustainable material R&D, tax credits for eco-innovation and subsidies for independent testing and certification.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner seeks also clearer regulatory pathways and consistent objectives – they note that policy goals sometimes shift or conflict, making planning and investment risky.

The biocide case study partner recommends design tools and digital platforms for SSbD that incorporate full life-cycle thinking and calls for better stakeholder coordination during material design, enabling compliance to be integrated from the earliest R&D stages.

B. Industry–policymaker collaboration: Evaluation of collaboration quality and areas for improvement

The three case studies indicated that the current collaboration between industry and policymakers is not sufficient to address the specific challenges of advanced materials. The cosmetics case study partner noted that when science develops innovative materials and the market must integrate them, regulation should adapt to their specific nature. The lack of alignment between regulatory frameworks and the level of innovation introduced creates uncertainty in approval processes, as highlighted in the previous sections of this report. They proposed more integrated and dynamic dialogue, for example through roundtables bringing together developers, producers and policymakers to jointly identify solutions for Green Deal objectives. The cosmetics case study partner also cited *Halo Science*¹⁶ as a good example of a global matchmaking platform that facilitates contact and follow-up between innovators and industry, suggesting similar tools could be adopted at EU level, alongside EU-funded training on green chemistry for hybrid materials.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner mentioned that ISO discussions are the closest forum they participate in but noted there is no clear hotline for regulatory queries. The biocide case study partner also highlighted the need for more dialogue, as policymakers often do not fully understand the technical and market challenges faced by industry.

C. Tools, training, and networks for navigating policy: Useful resources for managing compliance and regulatory knowledge

¹⁵ **Green Claims Directive** European Commission. *Proposal for a Directive on substantiation and communication of explicit environmental claims (Green Claims Directive)*. COM (2023) 166 final. [EUR-Lex - 52023PC0166 - EN - EUR-Lex](#)

¹⁶ **HALO Science** Industry collaboration platform mentioned in one of the interviews. Website: <https://www.halo.science/>

Across the case studies, there was agreement on the value of stronger tools, training, and networks to help companies navigate complex regulatory requirements. The cosmetics case study partner stressed the need for dedicated tools and solid networks as effective means to manage and meet policy demands. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner noted that for SMEs, there is rarely staff dedicated solely to regulatory monitoring, as focus is often on market requirements, with cost-effectiveness remaining the core driver - although market demands can sometimes align with regulations. The biocide case study partner highlighted the importance of EU projects such as SUNRISE, where interdisciplinary collaboration and integrated platforms play a key role in supporting both development and compliance.

D. Lifecycle stage challenges in policy implementation: Most difficult lifecycle phases regarding environmental regulations

Across the three case studies, the most demanding lifecycle phases for complying with environmental regulations are synthesis and end-of-life, with manufacturing also presenting significant challenges in some cases.

For the cosmetics case study partner, synthesis remains a critical bottleneck, as traditional methods often lack the flexibility needed to integrate more sustainable practices. However, targeted interventions, where a highly impactful precursor was replaced with a safer alternative - have already delivered tangible benefits, notably reducing operator exposure during production.

End-of-life, together with the use phase, is equally complex, particularly for hybrid AdMa. These require a dedicated regulatory framework that recognises the unique behaviour of surface-modified nanomaterials. Under current systems like REACH, hybrids such as TiO₂-sodium surfactant are registered as separate components rather than as a single entity, allowing competitors to bypass scrutiny and masking potential synergistic effects. The differing degradation pathways - TiO₂ persisting in the environment versus the biodegradability of surfactant - underscore the need for hybrid-specific end-of-life criteria that also account for possible dissociation.

The cosmetics case study partner further stressed that regulatory adaptation is slow, delaying the development and market introduction of safer, sustainable innovations. Recommendations include pilot-scale funding, relaxation of GMP requirements during early testing under the SSbD principles, and SME-oriented mechanisms such as "Green Compliance Vouchers" to ease financial burdens. They also noted that well-designed standardization, much like ISO certification, can boost both quality and market reputation.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner reported that the lifecycle phase demanding the most extensive testing constitutes their main challenge, as the regulatory requirements here are both time- and resource-intensive.

For the biocide case study partner, manufacturing is the most sensitive stage, especially when handling concentrated essential oils. This requires stringent occupational safety measures, careful waste management practices, and compliance with multiple overlapping regulations, all of which increase operational complexity and cost.

4.6. VISION AND FUTURE OUTLOOK

In this section, the case study partners were invited to share their views on the future of advanced materials within the context of the European Green Deal. The discussion focused on how they foresee the evolution of their sectors, the expected regulatory and technological developments, and the potential long-term impact of sustainability-driven policies on innovation and competitiveness.

A. Future outlook for Advanced Materials under the Green Deal

Across the three case studies, there is a shared belief that the evolution of AdMa within the Green Deal framework is not only possible but essential. For the cosmetics case study partner, this transition is framed as both an opportunity and a necessity, as regulations increasingly prioritise sustainability, safety, and circularity. Advanced materials - being inherently smarter and more flexible than traditional alternatives - are well-positioned to meet these rising expectations. They draw parallels with the adoption of ISO certification, noting that companies became proud to comply once the ISO certification gained recognition; the same cultural shift could occur under the Green Deal framework. Regulation, they argue, can help complying companies justify higher prices in the face of cheap, non-compliant imports, while targeted bans - such as those on toxic UV filters like oxybenzone- have already opened market space for safer, innovative hybrids.

The Hyaluronic acid project, which transformed grape waste into a high-value product under EU bioeconomy incentives, is cited as a concrete example of regulation driving value creation. From a risk management perspective, starting with inherently safe components, reduces the likelihood of failure in regulatory assessments, even further within the product life cycle. Moreover, embedding SSbD principles from the outset can lower R&D uncertainty and strengthen consumer trust - particularly in markets like cosmetics, where EU rules are among the strictest globally and thus serve as a strong quality benchmark.

The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner anticipates progress towards Green Deal trends, with bio-based materials likely to expand due to their current lower level of technological maturity. However, they stress the challenge of maintaining functionality while meeting sustainability goals, suggesting that greener production processes will advance more rapidly than the development of entirely new green materials.

For the biocide case study partner, the short-term outlook is for gradual change, but they express optimism for a fundamental transformation in chemical production within the next 20–30 years. Such a shift is seen as both necessary and inevitable if emission reduction targets and broader sustainability commitments are to be met.

B. Reflections and recommendations on policy and regulatory frameworks

In addition to sharing their future outlook, the case studies partners were also invited to give feedback and recommendations on policy development and implementation. The discussion addressed key aspects such as support for sustainable materials, the impact of the Green Deal on sectoral competition, feedback on the SSbD framework, and awareness of other public consultations. Their insights highlight how policy frameworks could be better aligned with industry needs to support the transition toward safer and more sustainable advanced materials.

For the cosmetics case study partner, a top priority is the creation of a clearer regulatory classification for hybrid nanomaterials - such as their UV-filtering titanium dioxide functionalised with sodium surfactin - to streamline registration and compliance processes. The partner of the Anticorrosive coatings case study similarly calls for clearer, well-defined targets, while the biocide case study partner emphasises that no entirely new regulations are required; instead, improvements in the implementation and the streamlining of bureaucratic processes, particularly substance registration, would have a more immediate and positive impact.

On Green Deal - driven sectoral competition, the cosmetics case study partner notes that companies already investing in sustainable materials face higher costs and compliance burdens. The rapid evolution of regulation risks putting smaller companies at a disadvantage, particularly if delays in defining standard testing protocols for hybrid AdMa continue to block or slow market entry. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner warns that in a global market, European producers will struggle to compete with countries like the USA or China, where environmental requirements may be less stringent, potentially limiting the adoption of the most environmentally preferable alternatives. The biocide case study partner, however, sees the Green Deal as an opportunity to differentiate their business through quality and sustainability, even in competition with large petrochemical companies.

Regarding the SSbD framework, the cosmetics case study partner highlights challenges primarily in synthesis, up-scaling, and end-of-life phases, where operationalising SSbD principles is most complex. The Anticorrosive coatings case study partner has had limited exposure to the framework and, within this project, is focusing on the use phase - specifically, application and exposure once coatings are applied and cured. They call for greater attention to the use stage. The biocide case study partner on the other hand, underlines that implementation is inherently complex due to the many actors (technical, toxicological, and regulatory) involved and that coordinated initiatives like SUNRISE are essential for integrating these aspects into a functional and operational SSbD system.

Finally, in terms of engagement with public consultations, the cosmetics case study partner admits to being unfamiliar with these processes, while the Anticorrosive coatings case study partner is not aware of any current consultations. The biocide case study did not indicate active participation either, suggesting that mechanisms for involving SMEs and research-driven companies in these policy dialogues remain underdeveloped, including the dissemination activities of such. Gladly, within many European funded projects, such as SUNRISE, incorporated policy work packages enable such activities and support SMEs in taking part to policy dissemination as well as public consultations that touch their business areas.

This set of insights underscores that while the Green Deal is widely seen as a driver of innovation and opportunity, its success in fostering sustainable materials will hinge on regulatory clarity, global competitiveness, operational frameworks that reflect real-life material lifecycles, and more accessible pathways for industry engagement in shaping the policy landscape.

5. SUMMARY OF IDENTIFIED POLICY ISSUES AND POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS

As a result of the conducted interviews, multiple issues concerning environmental policies were identified within the three SUNRISE case studies. However, to address these issues, the case study partners also proposed solutions that, in their view, could help in the mitigation of the identified issues or gaps in the future. They are collected in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Policy issues identified by the case studies and proposed solutions

Policy issue or gap	Proposed solution
Lack of clear classification for hybrid and surface-functionalised materials	Proposed: Develop specific classification and registration categories for hybrid nanomaterials (e.g., TiO ₂ and surfactin) under REACH and Cosmetics Regulation.
Outdated and inflexible technical standards	Proposed: Active participation in ISO committees (e.g., ISO/TC 35/SC 14) to update coating standards.
Excessive costs and time for registration of natural substances	Proposed: Streamline phytosanitary registration procedures for natural, low-risk active substances and improve coordination with Green Deal sustainability goals.
Lack of standardized safety testing for hybrid and novel materials	Proposed: Treat hybrid materials as new entities in safety assessments; introduce flexibility in pilot-scale testing (e.g., relaxed GMP under SSbD). Additional suggestion: Develop SSbD-aligned, tiered testing protocols for hybrids, including dissociation and life-cycle analysis.
Fragmentation across sectoral regulations (REACH, CLP, Cosmetics, PPPs)	Proposed: Improve harmonization of data requirements across regulatory frameworks. Align definitions, data standards, and assessment criteria for advanced materials.
Weak data transparency and incomplete safety documentation (SDS/TDS)	Proposed: Build internal databases to generate material-specific SDSs for formulations. Develop an EU-level anonymised database for advanced material characterization data collected from EU-funded projects.
Slow policy adaptation and limited industry–policymaker dialogue	Proposed: Establish structured roundtables bringing together developers, producers, and policymakers; replicate global matchmaking platforms like Halo Science at EU level. Launch regular thematic workshops connecting SMEs, regulators, and researchers.
Lack of clear guidance and practical tools for SSbD implementation	Proposed: Create design tools and digital platforms integrating life-cycle and multi-actor coordination for SSbD application.

Green Deal implementation challenges and global competitiveness	Proposed: Introduce financial support measures (e.g., R&D funding, tax credits, compliance vouchers) to reduce SME compliance costs.
Misalignment between Green Deal ambitions and current policy tools	Proposed: Make the Green Claims Regulation binding to prevent false sustainability claims.

6. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, interviews across three industrial case studies on AdMa and within the SUNRISE project were conducted. These included case studies on cosmetics, Anticorrosive coatings, and biocides for post-harvest preservation. The results of these interviews underscore the urgent need for regulatory adaptation to keep pace with innovation in AdMa, while ensuring safety and supporting market uptake. Although each case study operates in a distinct sector, several cross-cutting conclusions emerged:

- **Compliance burden:** Current regulatory requirements place disproportionate strain on SMEs and research-driven developers, particularly when dealing with novel or natural substances. Both the cosmetics and the Anticorrosive coatings case studies emphasised the difficulty of dedicating sufficient resources to regulatory compliance, particularly when materials fall outside established categories or when testing requirements become costly.
- **Regulatory and standardization framework gaps:** all case studies identified that existing regulatory frameworks are ill-suited to emerging material formats such as hybrids, nanocoatings, and bio-based or natural alternatives, leaving innovators without clear pathways to compliance. For example, hybrid materials lack clear classification and testing protocols, innovative nanocoatings conflict with outdated performance standards, and natural substances face long and costly phytosanitary approval processes.
- **Safety data deficiencies:** There is a persistent lack of standardized safety data for non-traditional materials, highlighting the need for adapted protocols and dedicated testing. In fact, in this case, the cosmetics case study partners highlighted the absence of standardized long-term toxicity assessment methods for hybrid materials, while the Anticorrosive coatings case study pointed to incomplete SDS/TDS information for certain advanced ingredients. The biocide case study partner's experience further showed how replacing harmful inputs with natural alternatives can introduce new safety and performance uncertainties.
- **Transparency needs:** Improved SDS and mechanisms for data sharing are essential to foster trust and enable safe innovation, also within the development of new materials.
- **Circularity and end-of-life challenges:** Achieving recyclability and biodegradability for advanced materials remains complex and requires both technical advances and targeted policy support. With the example of the difficulty of assessing biodegradation of hybrid UV filters or polymer recycling. Additionally, natural extraction processes must be evaluated for overall environmental performance.

To address these issues, policy frameworks should evolve to:

- **Provide clearer and more harmonized information and labelling approaches** to reflect new material categories (i.e. hybrid and surface-modified materials).
- **Enable cross-sector alignment and harmonization of standards and testing methods** to assess transformation, degradation, and release under relevant conditions, reflecting the new material innovations.

- **Incorporate natural and hybrid materials explicitly into policy frameworks** and regulations such as REACH and CLP.
- **Provide clearer guidance and support** for safe innovation and compliance on AdMa, including transparency and adapted safety protocols.

These policy issues and recommendations are especially destined to the attention of the following policy stakeholders identified within the SUNRISE project (without any particular order of importance):

- European Commission
- European Chemicals Agency (ECHA)
- Joint Research Centre (JRC)
- European Food Safety Authority (EFSA)
- European Committee for Standardization (CEN)
- Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD)

In conclusion, the policy landscape should shift from reactive compliance to proactive facilitation of sustainable innovation. By modernizing regulations, closing data gaps, and supporting SMEs, Europe can ensure that advanced materials contribute to the objectives of the European Green Deal while safeguarding health, safety, and the environment.

7. ANNEX

7.1. Draft template for case study interviews/Survey

A. General Context

1. Can you briefly describe your case study and the advanced materials being used in your final products?
2. What are the main sustainability goals you want to achieve in your products/processes (e.g., circularity, biodegradability, reduced emissions)?
3. Are you currently aware of the European Green Deal and its potential impact on your sector? How do you perceive it? What are the specificities of the Green Deal that are mostly affecting your business?

B. Regulatory Awareness and Usage

1. Which EU regulations and directives currently influence your work with advanced materials? (e.g., REACH, CLP Regulation, Regulations for packaging, etc.). Which stages of the life cycle these are affecting?
2. Do you use any voluntary certifications or standards (e.g., Ecolabels, ISO standards) to ensure compliance or improve marketability? If yes, which ones?
3. Do you feel sufficiently informed about upcoming changes or new legislation related to the Green Deal or other European high-level policies? If yes, how do you stay updated?

C. Challenges and Gaps

1. Which specific (current or up-coming) regulations or requirements are the most difficult to comply with when developing or marketing (your) products with advanced materials? Why?
2. Have you faced any challenges related to material safety assessments, data availability, or transparency requirements especially concerning advanced materials? What are these challenges?
3. Are there gaps, overlaps or shortcomings in the current legislative framework that you believe should be addressed? Which?
4. Do you find the process of integrating eco-design principles into your advanced materials/products straightforward or challenging under the current regulatory framework? What are the advantages and challenges you find currently?
5. Are there any specific challenges you face regarding circularity requirements (e.g., recyclability, biodegradability)?

D. Opportunities and Areas of Ease

1. Are there any specific regulations or aspects of the Green Deal or other European Policies that have helped streamline your processes or supported your sustainability goals?
2. Have you found opportunities for innovation or market advantage due to new regulatory/policy requirements?
3. Is there a part of the regulatory/policy process that you consider particularly clear or easy to work with and that could be an example for others?

E. Implementation and Support Needs

1. What kind of support or resources would make it easier for you to comply with Green Deal or other European Policy-aligned regulations? (e.g., clearer guidelines, technical assistance, financial incentives).
2. Do you think the current collaboration between industry and policymakers is sufficient to address your challenges? If not, please explain.
3. Are there tools, training, or networks that you think could help your company navigate regulatory/policy related requirements more effectively?
4. Which part of the product life cycle you consider to be most challenging in terms of environmental policy implementation?

F. Vision and Future Outlook

1. How do you see the future of advanced materials evolving under the Green Deal framework and the related legislations?
2. What additional legislative or policy changes would you like to see to better support your work with sustainable and advanced materials?
3. Do you think the Green Deal will create a more level playing field for sustainability in your business sector, or do you fear it might increase the competitive pressure?
4. As part of the upcoming public consultation on the revision of the Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, please provide your feedback on methods development, specific improvements, or any other suggestions you would like to contribute. What aspects of SSbD are most important to you, and what would you like to see addressed in the revised framework?
5. Are you aware of/have you identified other (current or upcoming) public consultations relevant to your sector?

Optional Closing Question

1. Is there anything else you'd like to share about your experiences with regulations and the Green Deal that we haven't covered?